

Evaluation Report for **TEBT-2023-0001**

Submission Title	Using bench protocol platforms to improve compliance with systematic review guidance documents and reporting checklists: proof of concept <i>(Previously: "A general-purpose protocol for facilitating standards compliance when planning systematic reviews")</i>
Submission Type	Single-Stage Primary Study
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8263468
Evaluators	Olwenn V Martin (ORCID: 0000-0003-2724-7882), EBT Journal Handling Editor, University College London Iva Sovadinova (ORCID: 0000-0003-0627-243X), Reviewer, RECETOX Kerry Dwan (ORCID: 0000-0001-6918-1215), Reviewer, Cochrane UK Monica Gonzalez-Marquez and Ines Schmahl, Reviewers, Forschungszentrum Jülich
Status	Accepted
Evaluation Date	12 September 2023
Evaluation Round	Revised in response to round 1 peer review
Recommendation	Accept

Acceptance Note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor after assessment in one round of editorial triage and one round of peer-review.

The handling editor did not request changes during triage.

During peer-review, the handling editor and evaluators recommended that aims and scope of the manuscript and its intended audience be clarified to align with the results presented, that, pending this clarification, user testing of the tool be conducted if appropriate, and that the clarity and readability of the manuscript be improved. The authors addressed these issues by disambiguating the longer-term goal and hypothesis that motivated this preliminary work from the specific aims of developing a proof-of-concept tool, and by implementing editorial changes to improve the readability of the manuscript.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8042147>.

Peer-Review Evaluation, Round 1

The structure of this assessment report is derived from the reviewer and author guidelines for Registered Reports (Chambers et al. 2023, <https://osf.io/pukzy>).

Manuscript title	A general-purpose protocol for facilitating standards compliance when planning systematic reviews
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7521844
Submission Type	Single-stage study
Report authors	Olwenn V Martin (ORCID: 0000-0003-2724-7882), EBT Journal Handling Editor Iva Sovadinova (ORCID: 0000-0003-0627-243X), RECETOX Kerry Dwan (ORCID: 0000-0001-6918-1215), Cochrane UK Monica Gonzalez-Marquez and Ines Schmahl, Forschungszentrum Jülich
Recommendation	[enter brief summary of the recommendation to the authors]
Explanation	[enter an “executive summary” of the recommended changes and reasons for them]

Summary of reviewer comments

This manuscript is a proof-of-concept study aiming to set the initial groundwork to test the hypothesis that compliance with systematic review (SR) conduct standards and reporting checklists can be improved by reducing the amount of experience required for successfully using such standards and checklists. The authors developed code and a template for automated creation of a draft protocol manuscript. This allowed them to develop a theoretical understanding of how such a system may improve compliance with research conduct and reporting standards. They identified specific and general issues that would need to be addressed to enable further development and testing of the proposed approach.

Importance of impact of limitations on study findings	A limitation of the study is that it is not clear who its intended audience is
Potential additional work to overcome limitations	[Summarise the tendency of the reviewers toward recommending additional experimental work, analysis, and/or revision to address the limitations]
Potential acceptability of characterising limitations instead of doing additional work	[Summarise the tendency of the reviewers toward characterising the limitations of the study]

Structured assessment

1. Are the research questions or knowledge goals important?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
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Comments: There is general consensus that the work is needed and of interest to the systematic review community.

Reviewer 1: The topic is both necessary and pertinent.

Reviewer 2: This is definitely of interest to the systematic review community but needs to be simplified somehow and considerations given to matters stated therein.

Reviewer 3: This is needed work.

Suggestions for addressing the comments: None necessary

2. Do the authors present a logical, rational, and/or plausible approach to achieving their research goals?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
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Comments: There may be some confusion regarding the aims and scope of the work described in this manuscript. Although the longer term aim is to test the hypothesis that the automated creation of a draft systematic review protocol may improve compliance with conduct and reporting standards, the aims of this proof of concept do not extend to actually testing that hypothesis. The aims of the proof-of-concept could be made clearer. Reviewers felt that the approach could also be clarified by characterising the experience and understanding that may be required of novice users of such a tool as well as the background information and guidance that would need to be provided alongside the automated tool.

Reviewer 2: There isn't much detail on the experience required for authors to undertake a review. There are concerns by the community that having a protocol template could allow authors to use this without actually knowing what they are doing and understanding the methods included.

Reviewer 3: Our concerns are that tool like this should make clear for whom they are intended, and that if intended for novices, then full examples should be provided along with definitions and explanations for all relevant concepts.

The manuscript's primary issue is that it isn't clear who its audience is. It often reads as if it were about to introduce conducting a systematic review to a novice but then the needed background information is not provided and key terms are either not defined or not described in enough depth, making the tool better suited for experts who want to simplify a process they are already quite familiar with. Our sense is that the authors intend for this tool to be useful to novices. If so, much more background information will need to be provided, beginning with what a systematic review is, what one is used for, and how it differs from a routine literature review. Also, the examples that are provided are disconnected. We're not sure if we misunderstood them and they do form part of a single example but we think not. For learners to truly understand a new process, it's very important that a complete example, no matter how simple, be provided from beginning to end. Each step must be described carefully, with all new terms defined.

Our recommendation is that the paper be reformulated as a guide to conducting SRs from beginning to end using the tool described here to ensure proper compliance, i.e. this is how you conduct an SR from start to finish and why (very important to clarify why things are done in given ways. Such a guide will then be extremely useful not only to novices, but also to e.g. instructors at libraries who are often tasked with teaching these kinds of skills. As such, a complete example with real information, even if it consists of a toy question, will also be invaluable. The key is that the different bits of documentation should have clear connections to each other so that learners can see and understand clearly how the different types of information in an SR map to each other. This is not clear in the example included in this version of the tool.

Suggestions for addressing the comments:

There is a need to clarify the intended audience for the current proof-of-concept, i.e. is the current proof-of-concept of interest for developers and experienced systematic reviewers, or presenting a tool ready to be used by novices? This represents editorial changes to improve the clarity of the aims and scope of the work presented, likely feasible and acceptable to the authors.

If the tool introduced in this manuscript were already intended to be "an explicit, step-by-step sequence of operational procedures", further analysis and experimental work may be necessary to ensure the usability of the tool for novice users, e.g. develop background information defining key terms as well as guidance and fully worked example. This represents considerable additional

work, may require additional funding and authors may select to instead clarify the aims of the current proof-of-concept template.

3. Is the methodology and/or analysis pipeline sound (including, if relevant, appropriate characterisation of its statistical power)?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
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Comments: There were no specific comment about the methods described to develop the general-purpose protocol. Reviewers identified the lack of user testing, either from SR specialists or novice users, as a major limitation of the work.

Reviewer 1:

1. While I recognize that this is a proof-of-concept project, I feel that feedback from users and systematic review writers who were not involved in the development of the protocol would be beneficial. Have the authors conducted any pilot testing and received feedback from users?
2. Furthermore, to be effective and widely adopted by systematic review writers, the protocol should be user-friendly and easy to understand. It would be helpful to know if there is any training available or planned for the use of this protocol.

Reviewer 2: There has been no user testing so it is difficult to know if this is a practical option.

Suggestions for addressing the comments: The lack of user testing has been highlighted as a major limitation to the work by several reviewers. The authors identify that a number of modifications and improvements may be necessary before the tool can be user-tested. Depending on capacity and funding, the authors may choose to conduct user-testing before publication of this manuscript but this is likely to entail considerable further work.

An alternative, as described in response to question 2 is to disambiguate the longer term goal and hypothesis that act as justification for this preliminary work from the specific aims of developing a proof-of-concept tool.

4. Are the methods detailed and clear, with sufficient raw data and code to provide for transparency and potential reproducibility?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
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Comments: There were no specific comments on methods or code. However, the readability of the manuscript and accessibility to a wider audience may be improved if language associated with development of software or automated tools was briefly explained and clarified.

Reviewer 2: The manuscript was difficult to read. In order to make it more useful, the language and layout should be considered again as to where it could be improved to make it easier to read.

Suggestions for addressing the comments: There were no changes to the methods for development of the tool suggested, only that the language used be clarified to increase the readability of the work and its acceptability to its intended audience. This represent non-negligible editorial changes but should be feasible and acceptable to the authors.

5. Are the authors' findings and conclusions justified given their data and methodological processes?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
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Comments: There were no additional comments related specifically to findings and conclusions.

Suggestions for addressing the comments: No further suggestions.

Other comments

Reviewer 1:

- 1.1. The authors should provide the spelled-out version and the abbreviated form of any acronyms or abbreviations the first time they are used in the text. For instance, in the first paragraph of the Materials and Methods section (P4), "PW" is abbreviated and in line two of page six, "API" is abbreviated without being spelled out first.
- 1.2. The reference manager mentioned in Figure 3 is "Zotero", not "Endnote 20" – P7/L6.

The structure for the peer-review evaluation is derived from the reviewer and author guidelines for Registered Reports (Chambers et al. 2023, <https://osf.io/pukzy>).

Editorial Evaluation, Round 1

Manuscript title	A general-purpose protocol for facilitating standards compliance when planning systematic reviews
Manuscript ID	TEBT-2023-0001 (232613986)
Handling Editor	Olwenn Martin
Editor ORCID	0000-0003-2724-7882

Triage Checks

Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	<i>1. Objectives, context, and mode of research</i>				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Clarity about the knowledge goals or hypotheses of the research (e.g. PECO) <input type="checkbox"/> Justification for conducting the research (context, rationale) <input type="checkbox"/> Differentiation between research in confirmatory or exploratory mode				
Comments					

Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	<i>2. Soundness and rigour of experimental approach</i>				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Theory as to how the experiment delivers the knowledge goal <input type="checkbox"/> Identification and authentication of experimental components <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sufficiency of power and replicates <input type="checkbox"/> Bias controls (e.g. randomisation, blinding, complete data, calibration & training)				
Comments	Given the objective of the work is to explore whether developing the operational process for SR protocol development would improve compliance with conduct standards and checklists (i.e. build theoretical understanding),				

	<p>there are issues regarding the structure of the manuscript and to what extent the current methods and results sections are aligned with this objective. A key question to answer here is whether the use of a hypothetical example for a SR protocol to demonstrate the use of the tool would be considered sufficient or if a real case study is necessary prior to publication.</p>
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Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	<i>3. Analysis of data and reporting of results</i>				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Data normalisation and cleansing techniques <input type="checkbox"/> Analysis pipeline (qualitative, narrative, and/or statistical methods) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Summarisation and visualisation of results <input type="checkbox"/> Selectivity in use of data or emphasis on study results				
Comments	The structure of the manuscript is challenging. Whilst this is related to the topic and development of a tool, some material presented in discussion should be covered results (and potentially methods).				

Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	<i>4. Transparency and reproducibility</i>				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Citation of data, program code, and methods (TOP 1 - L3) <input type="checkbox"/> Provision of code, data, and materials for third-party replication (TOP 2,3,4 - L2) <input type="checkbox"/> Appropriateness and/or implementation of reporting checklist (TOP 5 - L3) <input type="checkbox"/> Description of and/or adherence to preregistered methods (TOP 6,7 - L1)				
Comments					

Domain	<i>5. Ethics and interests</i>				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Informativeness of declarations of interests <input type="checkbox"/> Ethical approval for research with human or animal material or participants				
Comments					

Summary section

Summary of compliance issues

What is the impact of the compliance issues you have identified on the publishability of the Working Paper?	Do you agree that it is feasible to overcome the compliance issues?
<input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Serious <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Minor <input type="checkbox"/> None	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
Guidance note: Seriousness of the issue is independent of effort required to resolve it. For example, not meeting our requirements for citation standards (TOP 1, level 3) may not require much effort to resolve, but would be a critical issue. Critical and serious issues must be resolved prior to peer-review.	Guidance note: Feasibility is contextual, but in general issues that require additional experimental work or analysis of 3 or more months duration, and/or would result in the study being a different unit of contribution, is less feasible. This is a subjective judgement, provided to inform discussion of how to proceed with the Working Paper.

Summary of manuscript, your overall impression, and suggested course of action

This is an interesting manuscript; the development of the tool is important to the field and the work is undoubtedly worthy of publication. Potentially because it relates to the development of a tool, the logical structure of the manuscript is challenging. I would be interested in hearing reviewers' views and suggestions in terms of organisation of the materials and presentation of results, i.e. what belongs to methods, results and/or discussion, with specific reference to the stated objective and research hypothesis. Another important question for reviewers to answer would be whether running the tool for a hypothetical example is sufficient to demonstrate its the successful implementation.